

COMPOUNDS OF HEXAMETHYLENETETRAMINE WITH SIMPLE AND DOUBLE SALTS OF COBALTICYANIC ACID AND THE NATURE OF RESIDUAL AFFINITY.

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Preparation, properties and the composition of the compounds of hexamine with the simple and double cobalticyanides have been described.

The capacity of hexamethylenetetramine to form additive compounds with numerous simple and complex salts is well-known. Its compounds with many complex metalocyanoic acids and their salts have been investigated by Rây and his co-workers in order to explore the nature of residual affinity and to examine the possibility of their utilisation for analytical purposes (Rây and Sarkar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 3903; Rây and Das-Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 519; Rây and Sarkar, *Mikrochem. Enich Festschrift*, 1930, 243; Rây and Bakshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 125). From a study of the composition of the compounds of urotropine with complex ferro- and ferricyanides described by Barbieri (*Gazzetta*, 1930, 60, 229) as well as with complex thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltic salts described by Rây and Bakshi (*loc. cit.*), the latter authors have shown that the capacity for association with water molecules for any particular cyano-complex increases with its simultaneous association with hexamine molecules; in other words, the partial saturation of residual affinity of the cyano-complexes seems rather paradoxically to intensify the latter. This apparent anomaly was accounted for by Rây and Bakshi as due to an electrostatic character of the residual affinity exerted in these cases. The nature of residual affinity may be regarded here to resemble that of "Field Valency", which is very much akin to what prevails within a crystal between molecules of one and the same substance.

Recently a number of compounds of hexamine with complex nitropentacyanides has been prepared by Voyatzakis (*Compt. rend.*, 1936, 203, 1365). Similar compounds were also prepared by the present author, but the work was left unpublished. Their composition are in close agreement with those of Voyatzakis. The preparation, properties and the composition of the compounds of hexamine with the simple and double cobalticyanides have been described in this paper. A comparison of the composition of these compounds of hexamine and complex cyanides with those of the complex cyanides themselves reveals certain interesting facts. The

capacity of the cyano-complexes for union with water molecules increases on association with hexamine, as already indicated by Rây and Bakshi, in the case of simple cobalticyanides and nitroprussides, but decreases, on the other hand, in the case of double cobalticyanides. This is apparent from the following table. Evidently an alteration in the strength of the electric field around the complex ion is the cause of all these anomalies.

TABLE I.

Original salt.	Compound with hexamine.
Ba_3X_2 , 20 or 22 H_2O	Ba_3X_2 , 2.5 B, 23.5 H_2O
Sr_3X_2 , 20 H_2O	Sr_3X_2 , 2.5 B, 28 H_2O
K_2X	K_3X , B, 6.5 H_2O —Rây and Sarkar (<i>loc. cit.</i>)
BaKX , 11 H_2O	BaKX , 1.5B, 6 H_2O
CaKX , 9 H_2O	CaKX , 1.5B, 5 H_2O
SrKX , 9 H_2O	SrKX , 1.5B, 8 H_2O
$\text{Ba}(\text{NH}_4)\text{X}$, 11 H_2O	$\text{Ba}(\text{NH}_4)\text{X}$, 2B, 5.5 H_2O
$\text{Ca}(\text{NH}_4)\text{X}$, 10 H_2O	$\text{Ca}(\text{NH}_4)\text{X}$, 1.5B, 7.5 H_2O
$\text{Sr}(\text{NH}_4)\text{X}$, 10 H_2O	$\text{Sr}(\text{NH}_4)\text{X}$, 2B, 3 H_2O

For the compounds with nitroprussides, where $X = [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{NO}]^{2-}$.

CaX , 4 H_2O	CaX , 2B, 8 H_2O	} —Voyatzakis (<i>loc. cit.</i>)
BaX , H_2O or 3 H_2O	BaX , 2B, 4 H_2O	
Na_2X , 2 H_2O	Na_2X , 2B, 4 H_2O	
K_2X	K_2X , 2B, 3 H_2O	

EXPERIMENTAL.

Barium Salt and Urotropine.—A moderately concentrated solution of hexamethylenetetramine was added, drop by drop, with constant stirring to a concentrated solution of barium cobalticyanide, prepared by double decomposition from silver cobalticyanide and barium chloride. The white crystalline precipitate formed was filtered, washed at first with 5% urotropine

solution, then with 50% alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. The crystals were afterwards dried in air. {Found: Ba, 25'6; Co, 7'29; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 21'75. $Ba_3[Co(CN)_6]_2$, 2'5 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 23'5 H_2O requires Ba, 25'52; Co, 7'3; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 21'67 per cent}.

Calcium Salt and Urotropine.—Prepared like the barium salt from urotropine and calcium cobaltcyanide; the latter was obtained by double decomposition between silver cobaltcyanide and calcium chloride. The white crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed and dried as before. {Found: Ca, 10'17; Co, 10'01; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 17'82. $Ca_3[Co(CN)_6]_2$, 1'5. $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 23'5 H_2O requires Ca, 10'14; Co, 9'97; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 17'75 per cent}.

Strontium Salt and Urotropine.—Prepared from strontium cobaltcyanide and urotropine as in the previous case. The strontium cobaltcyanide was prepared from silver cobaltcyanide and strontium chloride. {Found: Co, 7'66; Sr, 17'08; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 22'52. $Sr_3[Co(CN)_6]_2$, 2'5 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 28 H_2O requires Co, 7'62; Sr, 17'0; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 22'62 per cent}.

Barium Potassium Salt and Urotropine.—A saturated solution of potassium cobaltcyanide (3'3 g.) was mixed with requisite amount of barium chloride (2'2 g.) and a little potassium chloride (0'4 g.) solution. On adding a concentrated solution of hexamine to the mixture, a white crystalline precipitate separated. These were drained, washed first with 5% urotropine solution, then with 50% alcohol and finally with absolute alcohol. The crystals were dried in air. The substance is moderately soluble in water. {Found: Ba, 19'0; Co, 8'12; K, 5'45; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 29'7. $BaK[Co(CN)_6]$, 1'5 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 6 H_2O requires Ba, 19'37; Co, 8'3; K, 5'5; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 29'6 per cent}.

Magnesium Salt and Urotropine.—Saturated solutions of magnesium cobaltcyanide and urotropine, on being mixed together, gave a white gelatinous precipitate. The magnesium cobaltcyanide was prepared from silver cobaltcyanide and magnesium chloride. The precipitate was washed as before and dried on the porous plate. It was finally kept over concentrated H_2SO_4 . {Found: Co, 9'1; Mg, 5'5; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 32'6; H_2O , 28'54. $Mg_3[Co(CN)_6]_2$, 3 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 21 H_2O requires Co, 9'0; Mg, 5'5; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 32'3; H_2O , 29 per cent}.

Calcium Potassium Salt and Urotropine.—Potassium cobaltcyanide (3'3 g.), calcium chloride (1 g.) and potassium chloride (0'4 g.) were dissolved in the least quantity of water. A strong solution of hexamine was added to this solution with constant stirring. The white crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed and dried as in the previous case. {Found:

Ca, 6'7; Co, 9'94; K, 6'59; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 35'5. $CaK[Co(CN)_6]$, 1'5 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 5H₂O requires Ca, 6'73; Co, 9'93; K, 6'57; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 35'35 per cent}.

Strontium Potassium Salt and Urotropine.—Potassium cobalticyanide (3'3 g.), strontium chloride (2'5 g.) and a little potassium chloride were dissolved in the least amount of water. The solution was then treated with a concentrated solution of hexamine in slight excess. The precipitate of white crystals was filtered, washed and dried as before in air. {Found: Co, 8'6; K, 5'69; Sr, 12'74; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 30'04. $SrK[Co(CN)_6]$, 1'5 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 8H₂O requires Co, 8'48 K, 5'6, Sr, 12'6; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 30'18 per cent}.

Magnesium Potassium Salt and Urotropine.—Potassium cobalticyanide (3'3 g.), magnesium chloride (2 g.) and a little potassium chloride were dissolved in water. A white gelatinous precipitate was obtained by adding a concentrated solution of hexamine in slight excess to this solution. This was filtered, washed and dried as in the case of the previous magnesium compound. {Found: Co, 9'3; K, 6'14; Mg, 3'8; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 22'1; H₂O, 34. $MgK[Co(CN)_6]$, $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 12H₂O requires Co, 9'3; K, 6'15; Mg, 3'78; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 22'0; H₂O, 34'0 per cent}.

Barium Ammonium Salt and Urotropine.—Ammonium cobalticyanide, prepared from silver cobalticyanide, barium chloride and a little ammonium chloride were dissolved in the least amount of water and the solution was treated with a strong solution of hexamine. The white crystalline precipitate was washed, and dried as before. {Found: Ba, 18'4; Co, 7'9; NH₄, 2'4. $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 37'6. $Ba(NH_4)[Co(CN)_6]$, 2 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 5'5 H₂O requires Ba, 18'3; Co, 7'87; NH₄, 2'4; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 37'3 per cent}.

Calcium Ammonium Salt and Urotropine.—The compound was prepared from the ammonium cobalticyanide, ammonium chloride, calcium chloride, and urotropine in the same way as the previous compound. {Found: Ca, 6'5; Co, 9'58; NH₄, 2'9; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 34'28. $Ca(NH_4)[Co(CN)_6]$, 1'5 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 7'5 H₂O requires Ca, 6'48; Co, 9'55; NH₄, 2'9; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 34'0 per cent}.

Strontium Ammonium Salt and Urotropine.—The substance was prepared from the ammonium cobalticyanide, ammonium chloride, strontium chloride and hexamine like the previous compound. {Found: Co, 8'98; NH₄, 2'75; Sr, 13'36; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 42'5. $Sr(NH_4)[Co(CN)_6]$, 2 $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 3H₂O requires Co, 9'0; NH₄, 2'75; Sr, 13'38; $C_6H_{12}N_4$, 42'7 per cent}.

Magnesium Ammonium Salt and Urotropine.—Magnesium chloride, a little ammonium chloride and hexamine were added to a concentrated solution of ammonium cobalticyanide, when a white mass was obtained. It was

washed and dried as in the case of the other magnesium compounds. {Found : N, 25.38; Co, 9.8; Mg, 4.1; H₂O, 34.0. Mg(NH₄)[Co(CN)₆], C₆H₁₂N₄, 11.5 H₂O requires N, 25.5; Co, 9.77; Mg, 4.0; H₂O, 34.2 per cent}.

Barium Sodium Salt and Urotropine.—Sodium cobaltcyanide (3.2 g.), barium chloride (2.3 g.) and sodium chloride (0.4 g.), were dissolved in the least quantity of water. The white crystals, precipitated by the addition of concentrated solution of hexamine, were washed and dried in air as before. {Found : Ba, 18.3; Co, 7.85; Na, 3.1; C₆H₁₂N₄, 37.85. BaNa[Co(CN)₆], 2C₆H₁₂N₄, 5H₂O requires Ba, 18.4; Co, 7.9; Na, 3.07; C₆H₁₂N₄, 37.4 per cent}.

Calcium Sodium Salt and Urotropine.—This compound was obtained as a white crystalline precipitate when a concentrated solution of hexamethylenetetramine was added to a solution of sodium cobaltcyanide (3.2 g.), calcium chloride (1 g.) and a little sodium chloride. This was washed and dried as before. {Found : Ca, 5.25; Co, 7.55; Na 2.8; C₆H₁₂N₄, 45.15. CaNa[Co(CN)₆], 2.5C₆H₁₂N₄, 8H₂O requires Ca, 5.18; Co, 7.64; Na, 2.98; C₆H₁₂N₄, 45.3 per cent}.

Strontium Sodium Salt and Urotropine.—A white crystalline precipitate was obtained by adding a strong solution of hexamine to a solution of sodium cobaltcyanide (3.2 g.), strontium chloride (2.6 g.) and sodium chloride (0.4 g.). The crystals were filtered, washed and dried as in the previous cases. {Found : Co, 7.82; Na, 3.0; Sr, 11.8; C₆H₁₂N₄, 37.9; SrNa[Co(CN)₆], 2C₆H₁₂N₄, 7.5 H₂O requires Co, 7.96; Na, 3.1; Sr, 11.83; C₆H₁₂N₄, 37.8 per cent}.

Magnesium Sodium Salt and Urotropine.—Sodium cobaltcyanide (3.2 g.), magnesium sulphate (2.4 g.) and a little sodium chloride were dissolved in the least quantity of water. On adding a strong solution of urotropine to the mixture, a white gelatinous precipitate was obtained. It was washed and dried as already described in the cases of other magnesium compounds. {Found : Co, 8.42; Mg, 3.35; Na, 3.29; C₆H₁₂N₄, 49.6; H₂O, 32.9. MgNa[Co(CN)₆], 1.5 C₆H₁₂N₄, 13H₂O requires Co, 8.35; Mg, 3.4; Na, 3.25; C₆H₁₂N₄, 29.74; H₂O, 33.1 per cent}.

Method of Analysis.—In the case of barium compounds, barium was estimated as sulphate by precipitation with dilute sulphuric acid from solutions of the compounds. The filtrate was decomposed with concentrated H₂SO₄ and the cobalt precipitated as sulphide. The latter was estimated as sulphate after conversion. In the filtrate from the cobalt sulphide, sodium and potassium were estimated as sulphate.

Total nitrogen was estimated by decomposing the compounds with concentrated H_2SO_4 and then distilling the ammonia with caustic soda (Kjeldahl's method). Nitrogen present as cyanide was calculated from the cobalt content. The percentage of urotropine was then calculated by difference.

With calcium and strontium compounds, the alkaline-earth metals were precipitated as oxalates from solutions of their compounds. These were then converted into sulphate and weighed as such. The filtrate was decomposed with concentrated H_2SO_4 . Cobalt and the alkali metals were then estimated as already described above.

With magnesium compounds, magnesium was precipitated and estimated as 8-hydroxyquinoline from solutions of the substances. Cobalt and the alkali metals were estimated as before in the filtrate after decomposing the organic matter with concentrated H_2SO_4 .

In the case of alkaline-earth ammonium compounds, ammonia was estimated by distilling the solution of the substances with caustic soda. Percentage of urotropine was then calculated by subtracting the amount of ammoniacal and cyanidic nitrogen from the total nitrogen.

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